

INTERACTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING METHODS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract.

To date, the actual task of higher education is the development of intellectual independence and social competence of the student. One of the methodological tools that provide a solution to the problem can be interactive teaching methods that are beginning to be used in higher education. The article discusses some interactive methods of teaching and learning in higher education.

Keywords:

Introduction:

Currently, there are cardinal changes in approaches to the organization of the educational process in higher education, due to modern trends in the development of higher professional education. The need to develop a completely new approach to the organization of education is determined by the introduction of a multi-level education system, the creation of a single educational space, and the implementation of a competency-based approach. The functions of a higher education teacher are not limited to the transmission of scientific knowledge; they also include the choice of the optimal teaching strategy, the use of modern educational technologies aimed at creating a creative atmosphere in the educational process. The educational process is improved by creating the necessary and sufficient organizational and pedagogical conditions that ensure successful learning.

In order to develop the basic competencies and meta-competences of students, to form the skills necessary for future professional activities, as well as to create the prerequisites for psychological readiness to implement the acquired skills and abilities into real practice, teachers should purposefully use active and interactive forms and technologies for conducting classes [1, 97].

While there is a certain commonality, active and interactive teaching methods also have differences. Interactive methods are the most modern form of active methods.

A student in interactive learning is the subject of learning activity to a greater extent than in passive learning. Entering into a dialogue with the teacher, he actively participates in the cognitive process, performs creative tasks.

Main part:

Interactive methods (from English interaction - interaction, impact on each other) are based on the interaction of trainees (students) with each other. Interactive learning: - is built on the interaction of the student with the learning environment and the corresponding environment, which serves as an area of mastered experience; - based on the psychology of human relationships and interactions; - is understood as a joint process of cognition, where knowledge is obtained in joint activities through dialogue, polylogue [2,105].

Interactive teaching methods, assuming co-education (collective and collaborative learning), are the most appropriate for a student-centered approach. Both the student and the teacher act as subjects of the educational process. The teacher, as a rule, is the organizer of the learning process, the leader of the group, the facilitator, the creator of the conditions for student initiative. Interactive learning is based on the students' own experience and their direct interaction in the field of mastered professional experience. Interactive teaching methods are characterized by the following:

- 1) activate the thinking of students due to the very technology of the educational process [2,174];
- 2) the activity acquired by the student with their help is long and stable;
- 3) encourage students to make independent decisions - creative in their content and motivationally justified;
- 4) the learning process is built on a collective basis and according to a certain algorithm;
- 5) increase the effectiveness of learning due to the depth and speed of assimilation of the material [7,133].

The forms and methods of interactive learning are diverse, and it is not possible to give a detailed description of each of them in a review article. We have considered one of the most used methods and technologies of interactive learning - case technology. Case (from the English case - incident, event; comes from the Latin casus - the form of the Latin verb cadere - to fall) - an incident that "falls, falls on us" [43].

Case technologies include: - method of situational analysis; - situational tasks and exercises; - analysis of specific situations (case study); - case method; - game design; - method of situational role-playing games [13, 1790].

As a form of training and activation of the educational process, the case method, forming certain competencies, allows you to successfully solve the following tasks:

- developing students' ability to think logically, clearly and consistently, to understand the meaning of the initial data and proposed solutions;

- development of skills of operational decision-making; - developing the ability to request additional information to clarify the initial situation, that is, to select the wording of questions that maximizes "development", "understanding";

- developing skills for visual representation of the features of determining optimal solutions under conditions of uncertainty and developing an action plan using a variety of approaches to achieve the desired result;

- acquisition of skills of a clear, accurate presentation in oral or written form of one's own point of view;

- developing the ability to make a presentation, that is, eloquently state, argue and defend one's own point of view;

- developing the skills of a constructive critical assessment of the point of view of others;

- development of the ability to make independent decisions, using a group analysis of the situation;

- the formation of the ability and desire for self-development and professional growth, based on the analysis (reflection) of one's own and others' mistakes, on feedback data [7,130].

A game is a form of activity (as a rule, joint) of people that recreates various practical situations, as well as a system of relationships and acts as one of the means of activating the educational process in the education system [10,687].

Understanding the game as a special type of human activity, closely related to labor, the professional sphere, led to a scientific approach to its study. About the game, as a symbolic model of professional activity, A.A. Verbitsky. The context of the game, in his opinion, is set by symbolic means with the help of modeling, imitation and communication languages, including natural language. Unlike other teaching methods, the game, according to the researcher, allows the student to feel personally involved in the functioning of the system being studied - he "lives" for some time in "real" life conditions, being "inside" this system. When considering situational role-playing games, it should be noted that they require more

spontaneity, individuality, creativity, and improvisation from students. A role-playing game, like a group discussion, can act both as a “cross-cutting” training method included in various exercises, and as an independent technique.

Thus, the game teaching methods used in the classroom allow solving the following tasks:

- the formation of new models of behavior among participants in situations of interpersonal interaction;
- expanding the flexibility of behavior through the adoption of different roles by participants in communication;
- study of behavior patterns that are effective in certain situations of professional interaction (for example, in situations of hiring, industrial conflict, customer service, etc.);
- a visual representation of the conventions of behavior patterns that are prescribed by roles, their certainty by the context of communication;
- formation of conditions that allow participants to recognize and correct their own inadequate behavioral models;
- elimination (or reduction) of acute feelings of the problem, which are caused by the situation being lost).

Thus, situational role-playing games are based on the organization of interaction in situations that simulate a certain cycle of professional activity. After the game, it is necessary to discuss the nature of the actions of the participants. The purpose of the discussion is to analyze the relationship between the "heroes" of the game, to determine the motives for their behavior, the attitudes in accordance with which the actions were carried out. In other words, during the discussion, both the adequacy of the participants' perception of the interaction situation itself and the appropriateness of the chosen ways of participating in it are determined .

In addition, the game as a method of interactive learning provides the following opportunities:

- Formation of motivation for learning (effectively at the initial stage of learning);
- Assessment of the level of preparedness of students (at the initial stage of training it can be used for input control, at the completion stage - for the final control of the effectiveness of training);
- Assessment of the degree of mastery of the material and its transfer from a passive state (knowledge) to an active state (skill);
- Effective as a method of practical skill development immediately after the discussion of theoretical material.

Role-playing games represent the largest and most important group of games used in interactive learning. Their essence is as follows - a person "accepts" a temporarily defined social role, demonstrating behavioral models that, in his opinion, correspond to it. As a rule, several people participate in the game at the same time - each acts in his own role. Participants perform roles that are not typical for them or characteristic, but in a completely different environment, which allows you to get a new experience of behavior. A situation is created that provides optimal opportunities for learning new behavioral models [33,411]. The role-playing game allows teachers to work effectively out options for behavior in situations in which students can potentially find themselves (for example, attestation, defense or presentation etc.). They acquire the skills to make responsible and safe decisions in a learning situation.

Role-playing games differ from business ones in the absence of an evaluation system in their process. Organizational-activity games are a form of collective activity during which training is carried out, as well as the design of new activity patterns.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that the purpose of these games is to introduce new practices in a certain professional field [34,415]. The interactive teaching methods considered in the article are aimed primarily at increasing the activity of students and their motivation for educational and professional activities. Their use makes it possible to move from passive assimilation of knowledge by students to their active application in model or real situations of professional activity, which, of course, improves the quality of training of future specialists.

REFERENCES:

1. Active and interactive educational technologies in the higher school: manual / T.G. Mukhina. N. Novgorod: NNSASU, 2013. 97 p.
2. Badalova, L. (2022). Development of the cognitive interest of students in teaching a foreign language at a technical university. Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 174–176. <http://conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/79>.
3. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2022). Formation of Intercultural Competence in Teaching the Translation of Economic Texts. Eurasian Journal of

Learning and Academic Teaching, 6, 14-19. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/801>.

4. Badalova, L. H. (2017). Teaching listening comprehension. Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука, (3 (2)), 42-44. <http://www.inter-nauka.com/uploads/public/14952665127664.pdf#page=43>.

5. Badalova, L. (2019). Accelerating Education, Individualization and Classification based on Developing Innovative Methods. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (1)<http://journale.auris-verlag.de/index.php/EESJ/article/viewFile/1041/1210>.

6. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS // ORIENSS. 2021. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/innovative-methods-of-teaching-in-educational-institution>.

7. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2022). NEW TRENDS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE. Open Access Repository, 8(03), 130-133. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/RK8HX>.

8. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2023). SOME FEATURES OF TEACHING SPEAKING IN ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers, 11(2), 823-831. View of SOME FEATURES OF TEACHING SPEAKING IN ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE (farspublishers.org). <http://farspublishers.org/index.php/ijessh/article/view/567/544>.

9. Bibalova S. A. Features of creation of lectures in the course of psychological and pedagogical training of students of technical college / Bulletin of Maikop state technological university. Iss. 3. 2009. P. 102-105.

10. Buriyeva, N. D., & Buriyeva, N. G. (2021). Teaching listening comprehension in esp classes. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 10(3), 623-627. indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:ajmr&volume=10&issue=3&article=100.

11. Burieva, N. G. (2022). National and cultural specifics of the verbalization of the concept «personality» in English and Uzbek. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 04 (108), 687-689. <https://oaji.net/articles/2022/679-1654871061.pdf>

12. Burieva, N. G. (2019). EFFECTIVENESS OF ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES. *Modern Science*, (8-2), 215-217. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=k9R_vugAAAAJ&citation_for_view=k9R_vugAAAAJ:UeHWp8X0CEIC.

13. Burieva Nilufar Gofur kizi. (2023). EFFECTIVE USE OF METHODOLOGY IN PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING. *International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers, 11(5), 1790-1799. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7992083>.

14. Dilnoza Buriyevna Nashirova, & Nilufar Gafurovna Buriyeva. (2021). THE USE OF GOOGLE CLASSROOM IN TEACHING ELT. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(11), 405-410. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/U2EM3>.

15. Hikmatovna, A. N., & Kobilova, N. S. (2021). Sociocultural aspects of linguoculture" clothing" in English and Uzbek languages, *electronic journal of actual problems of modern science. education and training*, 18-21. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=3281129292436106770&hl=ru&as_sdt=2005&as_ylo=2023&as_yhi=2023.

16. KOBILOVA, N. Literary Psychology and the Principle of the Epic Image. *JournalNX*, 7(02), 306-309. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/342765-literary-psychology-and-the-principle-of-1cb9cf8a.pdf>.

17. Nashirova, D. B., & Buriyeva, N. G. (2019). ABOUT SOME METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF WORKING WITH A TEXT AT LESSONS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Modern Science*, (9-2), 159-161. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=3361729375814427794&hl=ru&as_sdt=2005&as_ylo=2021&as_yhi=2021.

18. Nilufar G. Burieva. (2023). LINGVOCULTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF "PERSON" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences*, 1(01), 117-120. Retrieved from <https://www.orientalpublication.com/index.php/iscrc/article/view/910>.

19. Nilufar G. Burieva. (2023). CONCEPT AND ITS LINGUISTIC STATUS. *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences*, 1(01), 133-137. Retrieved from <https://orientalpublication.com/index.php/iscrc/article/view/908>.

20. Nilufar G. Burieva. (2023). THE CONCEPT AND ITS LINGUISTIC STATUS AND LINGUISTIC EXPRESSION. *American Journal Of Philological Sciences*, 3(01), 19-24. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/Volume03Issue01-05>

21. Niyazova Yulduz Tashmuradovna. (2023). GAMIFICATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY.

International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers, 11(2), 912–917. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689661>.

22. Niyazova Yu. T. Comprehend simple grammatical errors and effective ways of teaching grammar / Yu. T. Niyazova // Міжнародний науковий журнал "Інтернаука" . - 2017. - № 5. - С. 43-44. - Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/mnj_2017_5_12.

23. Niyazova, Y. (2022). BASIC PRINCIPLES OF LISTENING TECHNOLOGY. Scientific Collection «InterConf», (110), 93–98. Retrieved from <https://archive.interconf.center/index.php/conference-proceeding/article/view/455>.

24. Masalkov I. K., Semina M.V. Strategy of case-study: methodology of research and teaching: textbook for higher education institutions. M.: Academic Project; Alma Mater, 2011. 443 p.

25. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Main components of organizing independent work of students // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/main-components-of-organizing-independent-work-of-students>.

26. Solieva Munavvar Ahmadovna, & Azimova Maftuna Shavkatovna. (2021). USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING English. Euro-Asia Conferences, 14–17. Retrieved from <http://papers.euroasiaconference.com/index.php/eac/article/view/519>.

27. Soliyeva Munavvar Ahmadovna, Nurullayev Bahrom Komiljonovich Information-communication technologies and multimedia in foreign language classes // Достижения науки и образования. 2019. №6 (47). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/information-communication-technologies-and-multimedia-in-foreign-language-classes>.

28. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna, Tulaboyev Bekzod Zamon Ugli The role of the independent work of students in the educational process // Проблемы педагогики. 2018. №2 (34). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-role-of-the-independent-work-of-students-in-the-educational-process>.

29. Solieva Munavvar Ahmadovna. (2021). LINGUOPRAGMATIC FEATURES OF SPEECH ACTS. Euro-Asia Conferences, 41–44. Retrieved from <http://papers.euroasiaconference.com/index.php/eac/article/view/529>.

30. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Teaching speaking for non-linguistic students // Проблемы педагогики. 2018. №2 (34). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/teaching-speaking-for-non-linguistic-students>.

31. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna, Murodov Bekhruzjon Teaching and learning English through information and communication technologies // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/teaching-and-learning-english-through-information-and-communication-technologies>.

32. Soliyeva Munavvar Ahmadovna The formation and development of professional-oriented listening in a technical Institute // Достижения науки и образования. 2019. №8-3 (49). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-formation-and-development-of-professional-oriented-listening-in-a-technical-institute>.

33. Saidov, X. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СОКРАЩЕНИЙ И ИНИЦИАЛИЗМОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 27(27). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8735.

34. Saidov, K. S. (2022). LANGUAGE EVOLUTION AND LANGUAGE ECONOMY. INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE " INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION", 1(4), 108-115. Retrieved from <http://academicsresearch.ru/index.php/iscitspe/article/view/1019>.

35. Saidov, K. (2022, August). TELESCOPIC WORDS IN MODERN ENGLISH. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 154-162). https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0,5&cluster=16168631530126395931.

36. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2022). KONSEPTUAL METAFORALARNING LINGVOMADANIY HAMDA KOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI VA TIL TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN ORNI. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(3), 594-600. <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/1055>.

37. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2022). The Principle of Politeness in the English and Uzbek Languages. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 6, 65-70. <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/799>.

38. Yuldasheva, F. E., & Gulomov, S. (2022, January). POLITENESS LANGUAGE PATTERNS IN REQUEST. In *International journal of conference series on education and social sciences (Online)* (Vol. 2, No. 1). <https://ijorces.org/index.php/ojs/article/view/152>.

39. Бадалова, Л. Х. (2016). Проблемно-диалогическое обучение как способ решения учебной задачи. *Молодой ученый*, (11), 1415-1417. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=26425135>

40. Бадалова, Л. Х. Процесс преподавания психолого-педагогических дисциплин / Л. Х. Бадалова. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2018. – № 11 (197). – С. 130-131. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/197/48690>.

41. Буриева, Н. Г. Approaches to teaching writing in English / Н. Г. Буриева. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – № 6 (140). – С. 411-413. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/140/39353/>.

42. Буриева, Н. Г. Using songs and music in teaching English to young learners / Н. Г. Буриева. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – № 6 (140). – С. 413-415. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/140/39354>.

43. Буриева, Н. Г. Teaching English as an additional language in multilingual classes at international schools / Н. Г. Буриева. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – № 20 (154). – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/154/40042>.

44. Буриева, Н. Г. Multilingual programmes for eal students and effective teaching strategies / Н. Г. Буриева. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – № 20 (154). – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/154/40041>.